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Cross-Industry Orchestration with Connected Vehicles for Beyond 5G/6G Services

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Terahertz Wireless Comm.: Increasing the capacity of wireless communications

Multi-Core, Multi-Mode Fiber Increasing the capacity of the core network Multi-core fiber, multi-mode fiber, etc.

NTN: Coverage expansion 3D Networks Simulator/Emulator, Optical Comm. Terminals, HAPS, etc.

Space-time synchronization

- + Inter terminal coordination
- + Non-GPS location system with WiWi (Wireless two-way interferometry)
- + CLIFS: Chip Scale Atomic Clock

Virtualization and AI

- + Cloud native
- + Highly available resource allocation
- + Network Control with AI
- + Autonomic networks

Network slicing in 3D Networks Network functions and resources can be dynamically managed and flexibly selected.

NICT's Beyond 5G Activities in 2024

Safe and Secure “Society 5.0”

- **Safe and Secure Society 5.0** is a human-centered, sustainable and inclusive society.
- Through systems that achieve advanced **fusion of the physical and cyber spaces**, we can solve both economic and social issues.

"Beyond 5G" for Society 5.0

Human-centric society for everyone to play an active role (Inclusive), to grow without social loss (Sustainable), and to ensure trusted life against future issues (Dependable)

Key Features for Beyond 5G / 6G

Depicting Future Life in 2030s

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National Institute of Information and Communications Technology

*Beyond 5G/6G
White Paper*

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Beyond 5G/6G White Paper

- English version 3.0 -

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Ver. 1: March 2021 (JP), April 2021 (EN)
Ver. 2: March 2022 (JP), June 2022 (EN)
Ver. 3: March 2023 (JP), June 2023 (EN)

- 5 scenarios showing future life in 2030s
 - [Scenario 1] **Cybernetic Avatar Society**
 - [Scenario 2] **City on the Moon**
 - [Scenario 3] **Transcending Time and Space**
 - [Scenario 4] **Light and Shadow of the Cyber world**
 - [Scenario 5] **Path for Life**

- Key technologies for Beyond 5G are identified by back casting from the future life described in these scenarios.

- Scenario 1: Cybernetic Avatar Society (CAS)
 - With Cybernetic Avatar, people can maximize their abilities and share the skills and experiences of diverse people.
 - A society where anyone can play an active role freely by using CA, free from time, space, and physical constraints.
- Scenario 2: City on the Moon (COM)
 - Cybernetic Avatars on the Moon for construction and resource mining
 - Moon Travel, Street View in Space
- Scenario 3: Vertical Flow of People, Things and Information (IoVT)
 - Extension of our active area to 3D with autonomous Drone, Sky-car, Sky-truck
 - Warehouse in the stratosphere

Chapter 3: Future Life in the Beyond 5G/6G Era

3.1 Scenario 1: Cybernetic Avatar Society

3.1.1 A Day in 2035: From the Diary of a Technology Development Manager

- 9:30–10:30 Telepresence meeting with executives from Tokyo headquarters to discuss new product planning while still staying at home in Kyoto

XR teleconferencing among 3D avatars (UC1-3). I was a little nervous when the president's avatar appeared in front of me, but I moved next to the president in 3D space, handed him a product VR prototype, and asked him to experience it remotely with haptic gloves. We were able to get his go-ahead right away.

Figure 3.1 Telepresence meeting

- 10:30–11:30 Participation in global disaster response event

Remotely participated in large-scale training event for simulating natural disasters (UC1-3). Using global core network technology, experts from various countries gathered in XR space to discuss matters further (UC1-1), and our products were operated simultaneously in each country using space-time synchronization technology. We were very pleased to be able to verify the effectiveness of our products in the event of a disaster.

Figure 3.2 Telepresence event

- 11:30–12:00 Respond to an emergency problem at a manufacturing plant in Thailand by instantaneous physical movement (9:30–10:00 local time)

A sudden notice was received from a manufacturing plant in Thailand that the production line had been shut down. We attempted to remotely control the manufacturing equipment by hopping on a local avatar robot (UC1-3) and we found that a part was damaged. The person in charge repaired the equipment remotely and was able to work remotely with ease without any awkward delay.

Figure 3.3 Remote response to emergency problem

- 12:00–13:00 Remote lunch while assisting my father, who lives alone in the countryside of Okayama

Using an avatar, I was able to enjoy lunch with my father, whose physical functions are deteriorating. I remotely controlled the assistive devices to help my dad eat (UC1-2). EEG analysis showed that his understanding had not deteriorated, which was a relief. This is probably thanks to the AI interactive nursing care system that my father uses every day.

Figure 3.4 Remote assistance

3.2 Scenario 2: City on the Moon

3.2.1 People Cultivating the Moon

Figure 3.8 Image of scenario – City on the Moon

<At the Lunar Gateway>

Everyone gathers in the briefing room with their favorite tumbler in one hand. This is a space station orbiting the Moon (lunar gateway). There are only four astronauts serving in turn. My boss shows a map of the lunar surface on the screen and explains the underground area to be explored today. One of the crew members speaks

Today's range is 70 percent larger than the typical exploration range. Aren't we working too hard?

My boss responds strongly:

Yesterday, the work was completed in another construction area. There are more than 30 avatar machines from Earth. Four of them can be borrowed from those construction sites.

After downloading the process chart and data, my boss and two crew members move to their own pods and start connecting to the lunar avatar machine (UC2-1, UC2-3). I pour the remaining lemon tea down the exhaust duct and slide into my pod.

Figure 3.9 Future lunar gateway

Figure 3.10 Image of lunar settlement and lunar base development*
*Space-X Base α: <https://www.theverge.com/2017/9/28/16382716/spacex-elon-musk-moon-base-alpha-mars-colonization-interplanetary-transport-system>

Actually happening, NOT science fictions

Scenarios in the white paper

Scenario 1: Cybernetic Avatar Society

Overcome limitations of BODY

Scenario 2: City on the Moon

Overcome limitations of TIME

Scenario 3: Vertical Flow of people, things and information

Overcome limitations of SPACE

Current situation

Cybernetic avatar of Minister Kono
developed by Prof. H. Ishiguro (Osaka univ.)
(taken at the G7 Digital and Tech Ministers' Meeting in April 2023)

OriHime Dinner (Oly lab)

Picture : <https://dawn2021.orylab.com/>

NASA Artemis Program

Moon to Mars
NASA Selects Four University Teams to Develop Technologies

Picture : <https://www.space.com/artemis-program.html>

Operation of flying cars
@ Expo 2025 Osaka

© Expo 2025

Picture : <https://www.expo2025.or.jp/news/news-20230303-02/>

Key technologies for Beyond 5G

T1. Ultra-high-speed and high-capacity wireless communication	
T1.1	Terahertz wave
T1.2	All-optical network (high-capacity optical fiber communication)
T1.3	All-optical network (optical and radio convergence technology)
T2. Ultra-low latency and ultra-multi-source connection	
T2.1	Edge computing technology
T2.2	Adaptive wireless network construction technology
T2.3	Adaptive wireless network application technology
T2.4	Autonomous localization, tracking and reservation technologies for radio wave radiation space
T2.5	Autonomous M2M network construction technology with super multi-connection
T3. Wired and wireless communication and network control technology	
T3.1	Network control technology (Zero-touch automation)
T3.2	Frequency allocation and sharing management
T3.3	Private wireless system management (Local Beyond 5G)
T3.4	Advanced wireless emulator
T4. Multi-Layer wireless systems - NTN	
T4.1	Satellite and non-terrestrial communication platform
T4.2	Optical satellite communication
T4.3	Maritime communication
T4.4	Underwater and submarine communication
T4.5	Cooperative control of multi-layered networks

T5. Space-time synchronization	
T5.1	Wireless Space-Time Synchronization
T5.2	Chip-Scale Atomic Clock
T5.3	Generation and sharing technology for reference time
T6. Ultra-security and reliability	
T6.1	Emerging security technology
T6.2	Cyber security technology based on real attack data
T6.3	Quantum cryptography
T6.4	Electromagnetic environmental technology
T6.5	Resilient ICT
T6.6	Sensing
T7. Ultra-realistic and Innovative Applications	
T7.1	Brain information reading, visualization, and BMI technology
T7.2	Intuition measurement, transmission and assurance technologies
T7.3	Real 3D avatars, multisensory communication and XR technology
T7.4	AI analytics and dialogue technology using language and extra-linguistic information
T7.5	Edge AI behavioral support
T7.6	Simultaneous multi-lingual interpretation, paraphrase and summarization technology
T7.7	Automated driving
T7.8	Drones

- The key technologies are extracted and categorized from the use cases.
- Beyond 5G/6G Services are created with proper combination of the technologies.

Physical Space

Cyber Space

Stakeholders of Beyond 5G/6G

- Services in 2030s are realized with variety of technologies.
- **No single organization** can build up a whole system.
- Operators, providers and individuals **bring their own** sub-systems.
- Sub-systems are **optimally combined**.

Network operator A, B, C

Sub-system

Sub-system

Sub-system

Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) systems

Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites

Geostationary earth orbit (GEO) satellite

Space/Moon

Hybrid links (radio, light)

Space-time resource synchronization system

Application systems

High Altitude Platform Station (HAPS)

Over the air, on sea, at disaster site

NTN ground facilities

Service provider a, b, c

Sub-system

Sub-system

Sub-system

Terrestrial Network (TN) systems

Terahertz band comm. system

Private cellular

Public cellular

Edge computing system

Optical fiber networks

NOT just network orchestration

- ❑ Orchestrator connect systems **across industries** to easily join the B5G world.
- ❑ With the **architecture**, players with subsystems can easily connect each other and create new services.
- ❑ The more systems are connected, **the more service combinations** will be created!

Seamless relay transportation over ground and airspace

Sustainable seafood ecosystem saving multiple resources

Working environment with well-being on the moon

	Vehicles	Decade to realize		
Active range	Connected Vehicle	2010s	2020s	2030s
Ground	Car, Track, Bus, Train	✓	✓	✓
Ocean	Ship, Underwater probe		✓	✓
Air	Drone, Air plain		✓	✓
Space	Spaceship		✓	✓
Virtual	Avatar			✓

VR/AR experience of Beyond 5G world ~ focusing on a supply chain

1 Scene from "Catch"

Fishes can be easily caught from fish school information obtained from HAPS, smart buoys, and undersea drones, and future harvests can be predicted in cyberspace based on current catch trends, etc. Furthermore, the "orchestrator" can accurately determine the required amount of fish demand according to consumer needs, so that fishes can be caught based on such information. This will help to stabilize the income of fishermen and conserve fishery resources.

2 Scene from "Cook"

In a fish processing plant, the cooking process is carried out by an avatar robot controlled by a professional chef, which improves sanitation, quality control, and the working environment. Furthermore, the "orchestrator" coordinates workers across time and space, allowing worldwide chefs to be brought together on the spot to meet cooking needs, and the avatar robot can be operated to quickly prepare food without compromising freshness, creating a new type of catering service that is like having a worldwide top chef deliver food to your doorstep.

3 Scene from "Transport"

Progress in automated driving technology and the development of flying cars will greatly reduce traffic accidents and congestion. Furthermore, the "orchestrator" can reduce energy consumption for transportation by coordinating among carriers, reducing the frequency of truck transportation by consolidating deliveries according to the destination, and transferring the transportation of freight to cabs in the middle of the route.

4 Scene from "Eat"

Shopping can be done from the comfort of one's home using an alter ego avatar in the supermarket. Furthermore, consumers can purchase fish directly from fishermen through matching performed by the "orchestrator", creating a new service that allows consumers to obtain rare fish. Food loss can be reduced by allowing fishermen to sell unused fish, that had previously been discarded, directly on board their vessels.

Mobile World Congress (MWC) Barcelona 2024

- Exhibitions from NICT
 - Dome theater showing future life in 2030s
 - Spot transmission for moving cars in 60 GHz
 - Uncompressed 4K video transmission in 300 GHz

Scope of Beyond 5G and 6G

Beyond 5G Architecture for open service framework

The platform should be **open**, where the sub-systems are optimally combined.

Architecture of the Beyond 5G platform needs to be discussed on **cross-industry** basis.

Ref.: Beyond 5G/6G white paper ver. 2, NICT, Mar. 2022.

- Key functions**
- **Orchestrator** discovers **adequate combinations** of the systems and **federates them** to satisfy the requirements from services.
 - **Service enabler** interacts with the services and the orchestrator to **hide complexity** of the CPS systems.

Internet Governance Forum 2023 @ Kyoto, Japan

Internet Governance Forum 2023 (IGF2023)
Oct. 8-14, 2023@Kyoto, Japan

- The 18th forum hosted by the United Nations and MIC of Japan
- Discussion on the Internet vision with experts from the world
- NICT organized a panel session

“Future Network System as Open Service Platform in Beyond 5G/6G Era”

Open service platform is required. Only big companies in very developed countries have enjoyed business opportunities so far.

Beyond 5G/6G has **not simply a brilliant future**. Related issues such as spectrum utilization and energy consumption should be resolved at the same time. **Cross-industry sustainable ecosystem** is required.

Panelists

Ms. Thabisa Faye

Councillor for Independent Communications Authority of South Africa, Republic of South Africa

Mr. Abhimanyu Gosain

Senior Director at the Institute for Wireless Internet of Things, Northeastern University, USA

Dr. Marja Matinmikko-Blue

Research Director at University of Oulu, Finland

Prof. Tony Quek

Professor at Singapore University of Technology and Design, Singapore

Moderator

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4K uncompressed video is transferred in very short time just while passing the transmission spot. Connection is established in less than 1 ms with 802.15.3e/3d compliant devices.

Applicable for drone-car data relay that has a severe time requirements to keep tracking each other.

- Higher bands have been said "**not suitable** for mobile communication"
- Not for "always connected", but for "**instantaneous transportation**" in case of moving vehicles
- Network system is a combination of systems with different features
- THz bands (mmWave bands also) have potential to bring new values in vehicles communications

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<https://beyond5g.nict.go.jp/en/>